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DEMOGRAPHIC STATUS LEVEL OF COMPLETE SECONDARY ADENTIA IN ELDERLY AND SENILE PEOPLE

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Abstract

The aim of the study was to study the medical and demographic prognosis in orthopedic treatment of secondary complete adentia based on literary data. So, among the elderly, secondary complete adentia in the Russian Federation and the CIS countries averages 8.9%. Over the next 20 years, the number of men and women with the diagnosis of secondary edentulism in these countries will increase by 4-7%. According to a pessimistic forecast based on the current demographic situation in the Russian Federation, the number of this contingent by 2015 will be 14.7 million, by 2020 - 15.1 million, by 2025 - 15.7 million, by 2030 - 16.3 million people. Dental medical and social aspect of rehabilitation of this group of contingents without oral cavity sanitation and the restoration of chewing function cannot affect the improvement of their quality of life.

Keywords: secondary complete dentulous, complete removable plate prosthesis, orthopedic treatment.

Socio-economic, lifestyle and psychological status of the patient, educational and cultural level, genetic predisposition, socio-demographic environment, impact environment, geographic location, complication rate and the incidence of the disease as a result of insufficient dental care in childhood, intensification Tooth loss plays a key role in rapid aging

The main features of the influence of diseases on physiological aging due to the complexity of the pathological condition, nonspecific the formation of diseases, rapid changes in the state without treatment, the frequency of complications, the need for long-term rehabilitation [5].

In a 1980 UN resolution, the age limit was set at 60 for as a transitional age for the elderly. Therefore, the term "older person" means a person over 60 years of age, and this does not depend on whether it works or not.

The dental status of the elderly is a system indicators of the socio-economic standard of living, reflecting their social security, general health and lifestyle, functional state of the dental system. At the same time, women lose more teeth than older and older men, regardless of age, social and general health, frequency and nature of dental care. It affects the oral cavity and general health status [8,9].

The declaration of aging is an irreversible change in living substance, covering all mineral, functional, psychological processes occurring in the body. Like a closed system life of a person develops at different stages, reaching its peak at the age of 45 years and ending with old age after 65 years. Chronologically, these

are 45-59 years, 60-74 years old, 75 years old and older, over 90 years old.

Currently, there is an intensive aging of the population in Russia and worldwide. According to Rosstat, since the end of 2007 in Russia 20.6% population older than working age.

In modern times, according to medical statistics, people's life expectancy is increasing. For this reason, among people secondary complete adentia is more common. It should be noted that in the US the number of people aged 55-64 will increase from 21,006 per 1,000 people in 1991 to 41,714 in 2020 This figure is 18,274 and 31,385 respectively aged 65-74 years, 10 311 and 15 375 people aged 75-84 years, 3,178 and 6,460 people aged 85 and over.

The elderly population has increased over the past 10 years by 2.7% and will amount to 2001, 1.9 million people, or 19.1% of the total population. In 2003 the population over 60 years old accounted for 20% of the total population of Belarus. Then, by According to the WHO, the population over 60 years old will reach 600 million in 2025 and 2 billion in 2050 in developed countries. For dental Russia characterized by an increase in the proportion of older people in the population. According to the latest According to the Demographic Center, one fifth of the population of Russia - pensioners. According to statistics for 2015, the number of older people increased by 20% of the total population, and in 2055 it is expected that the number of older people will reach 40-55% of the total population. Such a prognosis indicates that gerontostomatological and geriatric examinations are needed to development

of an effective rehabilitation program for the elderly and fully edentulous patients in the elderly [6].

The number of people over the age of 64 in the former USSR is projected to increase by 8% in 2025 compared to 1980 (United Nations, 1982). In the next century, the number of older people will be proportional to increase. Most people are in transition as the population over 60 years of age will double since 2000, especially in European continent, where an aging population will be particularly affected. This suggests that by 2025 one in seven people will be over 60 years.

Borisenko L.G. [3] Belarus is very interesting, because in most developed countries, there is a trend towards an increase in the number of older people. According to official statistics, in practice the number of patients in aged 60 years and older in the republic increases with statistical the results of providing dental care to the population and integrated approach to it. In the near future, it is expected that visits to the dentist among the elderly will reach 75%. The number of completely edentulous patients varies depending on their age and gender.

According to the studies of B.Kh. Kopeikin and M.Z. Mirgazizov [13], quickly the incidence of complete tooth loss is increasing (five times more than in each next age group), and in Russia secondary complete adentia teeth in 1% of cases between the age of 40- 9, 50-59 years 5.5% of cases falls between the ages of 60 and 25. Secondary complete edentulous common among the elderly and senile. 40% of people older than 65 years are completely devoid of teeth. Only 2% of them completely all 28 teeth were preserved.

According to WHO, the frequency of secondary complete dentition in one or both jaws is high worldwide. In Canada, 30-40% of people over 30 years have no teeth at all. Mean age of complete tooth loss The Netherlands is 44 years old. Australia has 228,500 people aged 15 years and older have no teeth at all. In the United States 48% Americans aged 65 to 74 do not have a single tooth in their mouth.

Medical care provided to patients in dental clinics departments of medical institutions In 17.96% of patients Secondary complete adentia of one or both jaws was diagnosed [7]. Zuzelman N.U., Marinello K.P. [22] found in approximately 60 patients with secondary edentulous, that more than half of them lost their teeth on one or both jaws by the age of 60. In most cases, tooth loss starts from the upper jaw. Especially in women, secondary complete adentia of the upper jaw begins on average 17 years earlier.

Most authors believe that the need for orthopedic-dental care is due to the prevalence dental diseases, the level of special services, medical geographic, social and demographic factors. Although the prevalence of tooth loss has declined in economically developed countries, especially in the USA, in the next 10 years the need for a fully removable dentures will increase [4].

Numerous epidemiological studies in economically developed countries abroad confirm that the state

of the oral cavity in the elderly population is not so satisfactory. In Germany 25% elderly patients use fully removable dentures for both jaws [1].

Due to the increasing demographic growth in the number of elderly and old age in recent years, the need for complete food dentures is high. In modern times, the age limit has become younger among a population that has lost all its teeth.

In recent decades, there has been a demographic increase in the number of older people, which is associated with an increase in the need for prosthetic structures [2].

In Sweden, to assess the dental health of the population (according to Federal Statistical Center age range of patients 15-74 years) 41% of the population had a complete set of teeth (28 teeth), 31% had dental bridges, 19% need partial and full dentures structures

According to E.N. Borisova and B.D. Minakova [3], prevalence secondary complete adentia was 10.9% at the age of 60-69 years, 13.5% in aged 70-79 and 25.3% aged 80-89.

The results of N.V. Kandeikin [10], showed that in 49.4% of elderly people age (60-74 years), in 39.7% of the elderly (75-89 years), in 3.3% of persons elderly and 7.6% of patients had secondary complete adentia, occurs in patients in the age group of 45-60 years. Prevalence secondary complete adentia in the elderly was 25%, in the elderly 54.9%.

The results of epidemiological studies of prominent specialists closely associated with oral health and social and physical activity sick. Of those surveyed (average age 67), 10% are active life. 34% of them completely lost their teeth. Of the patients, 36% were inactive lifestyle (5 or more diseases) and 51% had no teeth [nineteen].

Human health directly depends on socio-economic conditions his life, and in people with a low standard of living, health is deteriorating [5]. Analysis of the situation of the elderly population of Russia in terms of social economic and demographic indicators allows you to select from this situation, there are three main blocks of problems: unsatisfactory health, low incomes and loneliness.

The aging of society is associated with the deterioration of human health. According to United Nations (UN), 80- 6% of older people have chronic diseases that reduce physical and social activity. The incidence of the elderly is characterized by the presence of many chronic diseases.

This pathology, common among the elderly, numerous works in foreign literature are devoted to this. At an elderly person with at least 4 diagnoses. With age, there is active course of a chronic pathological process.

It should be added that after 65 years, 56% of people were diagnosed with cardiovascular diseases (angina pectoris, SLE, hypertension disease, thrombosis), 44% - arthritis, 7% - diabetes, 87% - other somatic and mental changes. comes .

Only 22% of older people are practically healthy. The rest suffer various diseases, and 34% have organ dysfunction. The incidence rate in the elderly is 2 times

higher than in working age, and in the elderly (senile) 6 times higher (etiquette).

Summary

1. The number of older people in economically developed countries in the near future among the general population will increase, which, in turn, will increase the need for dental orthopedic assistance in connection with the complete loss of teeth

2. It is required to improve the orthopedic dental assistance to completely toothless people, which necessarily requires a report on individual features of the dentoalveolar system and changes the patient's attitude to oral health, as well as the applied dental prostheses [2].

3. Dental medical and social aspect of the rehabilitation of patients elderly and senile age cannot be considered as complete a complex of dental care without sanitation of the oral cavity and restoration of chewing function and, naturally, cannot improve their quality of life.

4. In this regard, the quality and level of dental care, provided on secondary training in the field of orthopedic dentistry with secondary complete dentition, depends on use of modern technologies in the design of dental prostheses [10].

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